

A 25-year survey of cardiac ion channel QSAR reveals near-exclusive focus on hERG, identifies barriers to multi-channel modelling, and outlines priorities for closing the gap.

25 Years of Cardiac Ion Channel QSAR: From hERG Dominance to Multi-Channel Modelling

Mateusz Iwan^{a,b,*}, Francesca Grisoni^a, Pedro Reis^b, Anastasia Pentina^b, Marina Garcia de Lomana^b, Alessandra Roncaglioni^c

^a Institute for Complex Molecular Systems (ICMS), Department of Biomedical Engineering, Eindhoven University of Technology, P.O. Box 513, 5600 MB Eindhoven, The Netherlands

^b Machine Learning Research, Research and Development, Bayer AG, Muellerstr. 178, 13353 Berlin, Germany

^c Department of Environmental Health Sciences, Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri IRCCS, Via Mario Negri 2, Milan 20156, Italy

* Corresponding author. Email: m.iwan@tue.nl, ORCID: 0000-0001-5151-4659

Abstract

In 2013 the Comprehensive *in vitro* Proarrhythmia Assay (CiPA) initiative proposed multi-channel assessment for proarrhythmic risk evaluation, yet ligand-based predictive modelling has remained largely single-channel. To quantify and explain this mismatch, we survey 146 QSAR and machine learning studies on cardiac ion channels published between 2001 and early 2026. Across this period, 90% of studies target hERG as their sole ion channel endpoint — a proportion reflecting regulatory incentives, data availability, and research inertia rather than scientific necessity. Although public data for Nav1.5 and Cav1.2 were sufficient for modelling years earlier, both channels received only isolated studies until 2022. Since then, multi-channel modelling has expanded substantially, with multiple groups now addressing hERG, Nav1.5, and Cav1.2 jointly. In contrast, two CiPA channels, Kv4.3 and Kir2.1, remain entirely unmodelled due to genuine data scarcity. Closing the remaining gaps will require coordinated data release (or federated learning) for neglected channels, methods suited to data-scarce targets, and standardised benchmarks enabling rigorous progress tracking — none of which individual research groups can establish alone.

1. Introduction

Between 1997 and 2001, at least four marketed drugs — terfenadine, cisapride, astemizole, and grepafloxacin — were withdrawn from the market due to their association with Torsades de Pointes (TdP), a potentially fatal cardiac arrhythmia^{1,2}. Subsequent research revealed a common mechanism: block of the human ether-à-go-go-related gene (hERG) potassium channel, which conducts the rapid delayed rectifier current (I_{Kr}), essential for cardiac repolarisation^{3,4}.

In response, the International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) issued guidelines S7B and E14, mandating both *in vitro* and *in vivo* non-clinical assessment of cardiac repolarisation effects, including hERG channel block, and clinical monitoring of the QT interval for new drug candidates^{5,6}. In the period since their implementation in 2005, and through at least 2021, no new drugs have been withdrawn for delayed repolarisation⁷.

However, assessing hERG block alone cannot explain why some potent hERG blockers, such as verapamil, do not cause clinical TdP^{8,9}. Subsequent research revealed that interactions with other cardiac ion channels could offset hERG blockade effects — a compensation mechanism that single-channel assessment cannot capture^{10–12}. To investigate these multi-channel effects, the Comprehensive *in vitro* Proarrhythmia Assay (CiPA) initiative was launched in 2013 as an international collaborative effort following an FDA-organised workshop. The initiative involved regulatory agencies, pharmaceutical companies, and academic institutions across multiple countries¹³. The CiPA framework proposed evaluating proarrhythmic risk through three integrated components: (1) *in vitro* patch-clamp assessment of effects on multiple cardiac ion channels, (2) *in silico* action potential modelling integrating these effects, and (3) confirmatory assays using human induced pluripotent stem cell-derived cardiomyocytes¹⁴.

The CiPA framework has been progressively adopted in pharmaceutical non-clinical assessment, with industry surveys indicating increasing use of broader cardiac ion channel panels beyond

hERG¹⁵. In parallel, regulatory pathways now allow companies to waive certain clinical QT interval studies when comprehensive non-clinical data (including multi-channel *in vitro* and *in vivo* assessments) demonstrate low torsadogenic risk¹⁶. However, the adoption of *in silico* modelling has lagged behind experimental approaches¹⁵. The same pattern appears in the QSAR literature: until the last few years — despite CiPA’s emphasis on multi-channel evaluation — computational models remained overwhelmingly focused on hERG alone.

This review surveys QSAR and machine learning (ML) models developed to predict drug activity at cardiac ion channels relevant to proarrhythmic risk, focusing on the six channels central to CiPA: hERG (Kv11.1), Nav1.5, Cav1.2, Kv7.1, Kv4.3, and Kir2.1. Studies employing purely structure-based approaches (molecular docking, molecular dynamics simulations) without ligand-based predictive modelling, those focusing on general cardiotoxicity, and models targeting non-cardiac ion channel isoforms are beyond the scope of this review. We trace the historical development of cardiac ion channel QSAR, evaluate barriers to multi-channel modelling, and identify computational priorities needed to support frameworks such as CiPA.

2. Ion Channels and Proarrhythmic Risk

The cardiac action potential (AP) is a transient change in membrane voltage that coordinates the electrical activity of the heart. In ventricular myocytes, the AP comprises five phases (Figure 1), each governed by distinct ion currents that flow through specific channel proteins. The shape and duration of the AP depend on the balance between depolarising (inward) and repolarising (outward) currents (Table 1). This balance explains why hERG block alone cannot reliably predict proarrhythmic risk. If a compound blocks only the hERG channel, the repolarising current is reduced,

Figure 1. Electrocardiogram (ECG) and ventricular action potential (AP). Top: Single cardiac cycle showing P wave (atrial depolarisation), QRS complex (ventricular depolarisation), and T wave (ventricular repolarisation). Bottom: Simulated human ventricular AP using the CiPA-modified O’Hara-Rudy model (aligned with the ECG timescale), with phases 0-4 and contributing ionic currents indicated¹⁷.

prolonging the AP and increasing the QT interval. However, if the same compound additionally blocks inward currents such as I_{CaL} or I_{Na} , the reduced depolarising drive may partially or fully offset the effect of the hERG block¹⁰.

Predicting the effect of a drug on a single channel is inherently insufficient to capture integrated system-level effects. Even a perfectly accurate hERG model will overestimate TdP risk when compensatory multi-channel effects are present. The scale of this problem is substantial: estimates from the early post-ICH S7B/E14 era suggest that up to 60% of new molecular entities that tested positive for hERG block were abandoned in early development¹⁹, some of which may have been safe *in vivo* due to compensatory multi-channel effects.

3. Survey Scope and Methods

We surveyed the literature through searches on Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar, using combinations of terms including: (1) "QSAR", "machine learning", "deep learning", "prediction", "regression", and "classification" (methodology-related); and (2) "hERG", "cardiac ion channel", and individual channel names (target-related). Initial searches were supplemented with backward and forward citation tracking. Searches were last updated at the beginning of 2026. We included studies that developed ligand-based QSAR/ML models for compound activity at CiPA-relevant cardiac ion channels and excluded purely structure-based approaches and general cardiotoxicity endpoints. The sur-

Table 1. Major cardiac ion channels relevant to drug safety assessment. APD — Action Potential Duration. TdP — Torsades de Pointes. For detailed channel physiology, see Lei et al.¹⁸.

Channel	Gene	Current	Phase	Role	Effect of Block
Nav1.5	<i>SCN5A</i>	I_{Na}	0	Depolarisation	Slowed conduction
Kv4.3	<i>KCND3</i>	I_{to}	1	Early repolarisation	Altered notch
Cav1.2	<i>CACNA1C</i>	I_{CaL}	2	Plateau	Shortened APD
hERG	<i>KCNH2</i>	I_{Kr}	2–3	Repolarisation	Prolonged APD, TdP risk
Kv7.1	<i>KCNQ1</i> ^a	I_{Ks}	2–3	Repolarisation	Prolonged APD
Kir2.1	<i>KCNJ2</i>	I_{K1}	3–4	Resting potential	Altered resting potential

^a The I_{Ks} current is conducted by a complex of the KCNQ1 α -subunit and the KCNE1 β -subunit; QSAR models typically target the α -subunit.

vey covers publications from 2001 to early 2026.

Our survey identified 146 studies that developed predictive models for cardiac ion channel activity. The distribution of modelled channels is highly imbalanced: 131 studies (90%) target hERG exclusively, while only 11 (8%) address two or more CiPA channels, 9 of which focus on hERG, Nav1.5, and Cav1.2 jointly. The remaining four studies model single non-hERG channels: two address Nav1.5, and one each addresses Kv7.1 and Cav1.2. No QSAR models were found for two of the six CiPA channels — Kv4.3 and Kir2.1.

4. Historical Trajectory

We organise this historical survey into three periods defined by shifts in methodology and data availability: Foundation (2001–2009), Consolidation (2010–2018), and Expansion (2019–early 2026). Full study-level details are given in Table S1 (methods and targets) and Table S2 (dataset characteristics). Table 2 summarises the methodological evolution across the three periods.

4.1. Foundation (2001–2009)

Following the drug withdrawals of 1997–2001, the first QSAR models for the hERG channel appeared in 2002. Two independent groups developed three-dimensional pharmacophore models associated with hERG block^{20,21}. In the same year, Roche et al. applied methods such as Partial Least Squares (PLS) regression and Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) to a proprietary dataset²².

Subsequent studies adopted diverse algorithms, particularly Decision Trees (DT)^{23–26} and Support Vector Machines (SVM)^{27–29}. Bayesian modelling approaches were also used relatively frequently^{30–32}, while PLS remained relevant throughout the period^{33–35}.

Molecular representations were equally diverse. Physicochemical descriptors calculated using software packages such as MOE, DRAGON, and VolSurf were the most widely adopted^{22,26,36–38}. Other popular approaches involved grid-based and pharmacophoric features^{34,39–42} or quantum chemical properties^{28,43–46}, derived from 3D structures. In addition, some studies relied on circular or fragment-based features^{25,38,47}.

This methodological diversity occurred despite limited public data. Most studies relied on fewer than 200 compounds, usually collated from the primary experimental literature or reused from previous publications^{1,20,36}. The largest public dataset of the period contained 414 compounds²³, the largest proprietary set included 1,979 compounds⁴⁸. Data scarcity encouraged methodological experimentation but hindered systematic benchmarking.

4.2. Consolidation (2010–2018)

The period 2010–2018 was defined less by methodological innovation than by data growth. The expansion of public chemical databases (such as ChEMBL⁴⁹ and PubChem⁵⁰) transformed dataset assembly from laborious literature curation to systematic database queries. Public datasets for hERG grew from hundreds to thousands of compounds: 2644 in 2010⁵¹, 4415 in 2013⁵², and 6690 by 2016⁵³.

Algorithmic approaches consolidated around methods established in the previous period. Support Vector Machines remained dominant^{54–57}, with Random Forests^{52,58,59} and similarity-based methods such as k-Nearest Neighbors^{60–62} gaining popularity. Gradient Boosting Machines^{53,63,64} and the first Deep Neural Networks⁶³ appeared late in the period but did not yet overtake

classical approaches in popularity.

Molecular representations followed a similar pattern. Physicochemical descriptors and topological indices established in the previous period remained dominant^{52,55,65,66}. Extended-connectivity fingerprints (ECFP) gained widespread adoption^{67–69}, while three-dimensional approaches, including pharmacophore-based features, declined in relative frequency.

Despite larger datasets and mature methods, the field remained narrowly focused on hERG. Single-channel studies of Kv7.1⁷⁰ and Cav1.2⁷¹ were rare exceptions. Multi-channel efforts were equally sparse: Obiol-Pardo et al. modelled hERG and Kv7.1 jointly⁷², and the CiPA initiative prompted two groups to develop models spanning hERG, Nav1.5, and Cav1.2^{63,73}. However, these remained exceptions. The regulatory shift toward multi-channel assessment was not yet reflected in the broader modelling literature.

This period also marked a shift in how models were shared. Earlier studies typically published model specifications within papers as regression coefficients, decision tree rules, or pharmacophore definitions. Beginning in 2013, studies began releasing executable code and public platforms: to our knowledge, Czodrowski et al. published the first open-source hERG modelling code⁵², and Braga et al. launched the first public prediction platform in 2014⁵⁶.

4.3. Expansion (2019–early 2026)

From 2019, two developments have shaped the field: the adoption of deep learning architectures and the expansion to multi-channel modelling aligned with CiPA requirements.

Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) have been the predominant deep learning approach, reflecting the natural correspondence between molecular graphs and GNN architectures. Variants including Graph Convolutional Networks^{74–76}, Graph Attention Networks^{77,78}, and Message-Passing Neural Networks^{79,80} have been widely explored. Groups also adapted architectures from computer vision (CNNs operating on molecular images^{81–83}) and natural language processing (RNNs processing SMILES strings^{80,84}). More recently, several groups have combined heterogeneous representations — graphs, fingerprints, and SMILES — in multi-modal architectures^{85–90}.

Alongside conventional fingerprints and descriptors, recent studies have incorporated learnt molecular representations as model inputs. These include latent embeddings from Variational Autoencoders (VAE)^{87,89,91} and representations derived from Large Language Models trained on SMILES or protein sequences^{92,93}.

Modelling beyond hERG has expanded during this period, progressing from isolated single-channel studies to integrated frameworks aligned with CiPA. The first models targeting Nav1.5 as a primary endpoint appeared in 2020 and 2022, both framed as classification tools motivated by the cost and throughput limitations of patch-clamp screening^{94,95}. The broader shift toward multi-channel modelling was catalysed by Arab et al., who across three successive studies expanded coverage from hERG and Nav1.5 to include Cav1.2, benchmarked molecular representations across all three channels, and explored semi-supervised learning to exploit large unlabelled chemical datasets^{86,96,97}. Crucially, each study released curated datasets and open-source code, likely lowering the barrier for subsequent groups to adopt the same three-channel scope.

Several groups have since developed integrated models for hERG, Nav1.5, and Cav1.2, predominantly employing multi-

modal architectures that combine SMILES, molecular graphs, and fingerprints^{87,88,98,99}. One study took a distinct approach, framing Nav1.5 and Cav1.2 models as components of a generative framework for redesigning compounds with reduced hERG liability⁸⁹. The three-channel scope — hERG, Nav1.5, and Cav1.2 — has become a de facto standard, reflecting data availability and the compensation mechanism central to CiPA’s rationale.

Datasets have continued to grow, though proportional gains are smaller than in 2010–2018, with ChEMBL-derived compilations becoming a new standard^{100–102}. Arab et al., for instance, assembled a multi-channel dataset comprising over 22000 hERG, approximately 2000 Nav1.5, and approximately 800 Cav1.2 entries⁸⁶. Previously curated datasets were frequently repurposed as external test sets, and open-source code, trained models, or prediction platforms now accompany the majority of recent studies.

5. Barriers and Explanations

The historical survey reveals a field that has advanced methodologically while remaining, until recently, largely concentrated on a single channel.

5.1. Data Landscape

5.1.1. Quantity

The distribution of public bioactivity data across cardiac ion channels is highly imbalanced, reflecting the historical regulatory focus on hERG. Figure 2 presents compound counts from ChEMBL⁴⁹ (version 36) for each CiPA channel.

hERG dominates with more than 22000 compounds, a consequence of two decades of mandatory screening following the ICH S7B/E14 guidelines. Nav1.5 and Cav1.2 accumulated substantially fewer compounds, with approximately 3500 and 2100 respectively. More routine evaluation of these channels accelerated after 2013, giving them a decade less data accumulation. The three remaining channels — Kv7.1 (217 compounds), Kv4.3 (57), and Kir2.1 (42) — have minimal public data, reflecting both the recency of their systematic assessment and the rarity of deliberate drug development programmes targeting these channels.

5.1.2. Quality

These compound counts overestimate the volume of data usable for model development because assays differ substantially in quality and comparability. Electrophysiology measurements provide the most direct evidence of channel block, with manual whole-cell patch clamp generally regarded as the gold standard. However, multiple electrophysiology formats exist (manual and automated patch clamp, two-electrode voltage clamp, and related electrophysiological readouts such as microelectrode arrays), and many datasets also include indirect proxy assays such as ligand displacement, ion flux, intracellular ion concentration changes, or membrane potential assays¹⁰³. IC50 values derived across these methods are not directly comparable without standardisation, and even within patch-clamp measurements, differences in temperature or voltage protocol can substantially shift reported IC50 values between studies¹⁰⁴.

Encoding assay context during model training could partially address this issue, but a substantial fraction of ChEMBL’s assays lack sufficient metadata to unambiguously identify the underlying method. Manual curation of individual records is not practical given the sheer number of source papers¹⁰⁵. For neglected chan-

nels — Kv7.1, Kv4.3 and Kir2.1 — the situation is considerably worse. Our survey of primary medicinal chemistry articles revealed that while inhibition against the full cardiac ion channel panel is frequently assessed, its reporting is often limited to a single sentence noting no meaningful inhibition at the highest tested concentration, with no description of the assay method employed.

5.1.3. Implications for Modelling

Kv7.1, Kv4.3, and Kir2.1 are difficult to model reliably using conventional QSAR approaches with current public data. Nav1.5 and Cav1.2 have less data than hERG but enough for model development. Arab et al. assembled curated datasets of approximately 2000 compounds for Nav1.5 and 800 compounds for Cav1.2⁸⁶ — both exceeding what early hERG modelling efforts required, given that the largest public hERG dataset available at the end of the 2001–2009 period contained only 414 compounds²³. However, Nav1.5 received minimal attention until 2020, and Cav1.2 models have emerged only within multi-channel efforts since 2022, suggesting that data availability alone does not determine modelling activity.

5.2. Explaining the hERG Focus

Beyond data availability, three additional factors contribute to this pattern. We infer these from the survey data and regulatory history rather than from controlled experiments, but the evidence is consistent.

Regulatory incentives and requirements. The ICH S7B/E14 guidelines (2005) mandated *in vitro* repolarization assays (typically including hERG assays) and clinical QT studies for most new drug candidates. This created immediate demand for hERG models as early-stage screening tools. The CiPA initiative (2013) recommended multi-channel assessment as a more mechanistic approach, but crucially did not make it mandatory. The 2022 ICH E14/S7B Q&A document allows companies to waive clinical QT studies if comprehensive non-clinical data — including multi-channel assessment — demonstrate low proarrhythmic risk¹⁰⁶. However, this remains an optional pathway; companies can still meet regulatory requirements through hERG assessment and clinical QT studies alone. As a result, the regulatory minimum remains single-channel-centred.

This creates an asymmetric incentive structure. hERG models address a mandatory requirement and offer clear regulatory utility. Models for other channels support an optional, albeit scientifically superior, assessment strategy. Until multi-channel assessment becomes a routine regulatory expectation rather than an optional pathway, computational efforts will naturally concentrate where regulatory demand is certain.

Physiological relevance and blocking frequency. Cardiac ion channels differ in both their contribution to proarrhythmic risk and their susceptibility to drug block. A systematic assessment of 30 drugs from the CiPA reference compound set demonstrated that hERG is the channel most frequently blocked at clinically relevant concentrations, followed by Nav1.5 and Cav1.2¹². Kv7.1, Kv4.3, and Kir2.1 showed minimal or no block at therapeutic concentrations. This study confirmed the compensation mechanism: low-risk drugs showed a substantial block of Nav1.5 or Cav1.2 along with the hERG block, while high-risk drugs exhibited a predominantly hERG block.

This blocking hierarchy helps explain why modelling has concentrated on hERG, Nav1.5, and Cav1.2. Channels rarely blocked

Figure 2. Cumulative unique compounds with at least one valid IC₅₀, Ki, Kd, or single-concentration inhibition measurement per CiPA channel, after assay-level and measurement-level quality filtering (see Supporting Information, Note S1)⁴⁹. Documents with unknown deposition year were excluded from the time series; full counts including these entries are indicated by diamonds. Counts reflect unique ChEMBL molecule IDs and should be interpreted as upper bounds — additional study-specific filtering (e.g., activity threshold selection, removal of conflicting measurements, structure standardisation, and deduplication) will reduce the number of compounds available for model training.

in clinical use generate less screening data and offer less practical utility for early-stage drug discovery. While CiPA’s mechanistic framework includes these channels for completeness — particularly for integration with physiological models — the practical utility of predictive models is greatest for channels that drugs frequently block.

Research inertia. Two decades of hERG-focused research have produced accessible community infrastructure — widely adopted datasets, published baseline models, and broadly agreed performance expectations — that lowers the barrier to conducting additional hERG studies. For Nav1.5 and Cav1.2, such infrastructure is nascent: only a handful of curated datasets exist (primarily ChEMBL-derived compilations), which are reused across the limited number of studies. Even when scientific value might favour exploring undermodelled channels, the practical effort required to establish robust modelling pipelines favours incremental contributions to the well-established hERG literature.

5.3. Reproducibility and Benchmarking

Assessing progress in cardiac ion channel modelling requires standardised benchmarks that enable direct comparison between studies. Currently, such benchmarks do not exist, making it difficult to evaluate whether methodological advances represent genuine improvements or merely differences in evaluation protocols.

Each study defines its own data splits, preprocessing protocols, and evaluation metrics. In particular, random splits can inflate performance by placing close analogues in both train and test sets, whereas scaffold- or time-split evaluation is often more reflective of prospective use. The choice between regression and classification formulations has also shifted over time, with early studies predominantly favouring IC₅₀ regression and recent work increasingly adopting binary or multi-class classification schemes. More problematically, classification studies employ widely varying activity thresholds — ranging from 1 μ M to 80 μ M across the surveyed literature — with no consensus on appropriate cut-offs for distinguishing blockers from non-blockers. These inconsistencies prevent meaningful comparisons of reported performances.

Table 2. Evolution of cardiac ion channel QSAR by period. Columns indicate methods and representations that emerged or achieved widespread adoption; established approaches from prior periods typically remained in use. Dataset size corresponds to hERG datasets.

Period	Models	Descriptors	Dataset size	Channels
2001–2009	PLS, DT, SVM	Physicochemical, Pharmacophores	<500	hERG
2010–2018	SVM, RF, GBM	Circular, Field-based, Path-based	500–6700	hERG; Nav1.5, Cav1.2, Kv7.1
2019–early 2026	DNN, GCN, XGB	Graphs, Learned embeddings	5000–25000	hERG, Nav1.5, Cav1.2

A hERG model claiming 90% accuracy at a 10 μM threshold addresses a different prediction task than another reporting 85% accuracy at a 1 μM cut-off, even when evaluated on similar compound sets.

The field lacks an infrastructure analogous to MoleculeNet¹⁰⁷ or CASP¹⁰⁸ that would allow rigorous progress tracking. Without such resources, the community cannot determine whether recent deep learning approaches genuinely outperform classical methods or whether apparent improvements merely reflect dataset differences, threshold choices, or publication bias favouring novel architectures.

Establishing such benchmarks would require consensus on data curation, fixed train/test splits, uniform activity thresholds, standardised metrics, and a community norm of reporting benchmark performance alongside novel results. The recent emergence of multi-channel modelling provides an opportunity to establish such standards before the literature for Nav1.5 and Cav1.2 becomes as fragmented as it already is for hERG. A detailed analysis of data, code, model, and platform availability across all surveyed studies is provided in Supporting Information, Table S3.

6. Towards Multi-Channel Modelling

Bringing multi-channel modelling to the same level of maturity as hERG prediction requires progress on several interconnected fronts, including: data availability, methods suited to small datasets, and shared benchmarks.

6.1. Data generation and sharing for neglected channels.

Kv7.1, and especially Kv4.3 and Kir2.1, are difficult to model with current public data. Addressing this requires either new experimental campaigns or release of existing proprietary data. The latter may be more immediately tractable: CiPA recommends testing new drug candidates against the full ion channel panel, meaning pharmaceutical companies now increasingly generate data for these channels. Release of even a fraction of these data, through precompetitive consortia or delayed public deposition, could make modelling feasible without requiring new experiments.

However, direct data sharing faces substantial barriers. Proprietary screening data may reveal competitive intelligence about compound libraries, therapeutic programmes, or assay protocols. A potential solution lies in federated learning approaches, as recently demonstrated in a collaboration involving multiple pharmaceutical companies¹⁰⁹. Federated distillation methods enabled collaborative model development without centralising raw data, yielding models with improved generalisability across chemical series. Adapting such frameworks to Kv4.3 and Kir2.1 prediction could enable model training on proprietary data without requiring their release.

6.2. Methods for data-scarce targets.

Even with expanded data generation or federated approaches, Kv7.1, Kv4.3, and Kir2.1 will likely remain data-poor relative to hERG. Methodological development should therefore prioritise approaches suited to small datasets. Transfer learning offers one avenue: CiPA channels share conserved pore architectures with the broader voltage-gated channel superfamily (or, for Kir2.1,

with other inward-rectifier channels), and bioactivity data for related channels may serve as useful pre-training data. Multi-task architectures follow the same principle: compounds that block hERG frequently also block Nav1.5¹², and joint training could exploit such pharmacological correlations to regularise predictions for data-scarce targets. Auxiliary tasks encoding properties relevant to channel binding — such as electrostatic profiles or membrane permeability, which governs intracellular access to certain channels (including hERG) — could provide additional inductive bias. Few-shot and meta-learning approaches, designed to adapt to new tasks from small support sets, have shown promise in molecular property prediction but remain untested for cardiac ion channels, despite the clear motivation that data scarcity for Kv4.3 and Kir2.1 provides^{110,111}.

6.3. Standardised benchmarks.

A community challenge — analogous to CASP for protein structure prediction or the Therapeutics Data Commons leaderboards for molecular property prediction — could provide the coordination mechanism that the field currently lacks (Section 5.3). Such a challenge would need to define fixed train/test splits for each CiPA channel, specify uniform activity thresholds, mandate reporting of agreed metrics, and provide reference implementations and baseline models. Standards established now, while the Nav1.5 and Cav1.2 literature is still young, could prevent the fragmentation that has made hERG benchmarking so difficult.

6.4. Integration with physiological models.

CiPA’s vision extends beyond channel-level predictions to integrated proarrhythmic risk assessment using action potential models. In principle, QSAR-predicted IC50 values can be combined with free unbound plasma concentration estimates and Hill coefficients to compute fractional channel block via the Hill equation. These values feed directly into action potential models (e.g., O’Hara-Rudy¹¹²) to simulate drug effects on cardiac electrophysiology. This integration remains rare in practice.

One barrier is that human C_{max} is unavailable until clinical stages. Provisional estimates from animal PK or computational ADME models could bridge this gap at earlier stages, albeit with additional uncertainty. Developing frameworks that propagate uncertainty from QSAR predictions through physiological simulations, or that provide risk estimates across plausible C_{max} ranges, could enable earlier integration of multi-channel data into safety assessment.

This integration also highlights the complementary roles of classification and regression models. While classification models (blocker/non-blocker) provide useful early-stage filters, physiological modelling requires quantitative potency estimates (e.g., IC50) to simulate dose-dependent effects. The field should maintain focus on regression approaches or develop models that output calibrated probability estimates across activity ranges. One approach would be ordinal classification across IC50 ranges with calibrated class probabilities, enabling downstream conversion to approximate quantitative inputs for physiological models.

6.5. From methods to practice.

Multi-channel modelling efforts have increased since 2022, but they remain far from routine. The adoption of multi-channel datasets by multiple groups following initial curation efforts demonstrates that community infrastructure can shift research directions. Without shared datasets, code, and benchmarks, the

current multi-channel momentum risks fragmenting into isolated efforts, as happened with early non-hERG studies in 2010-2018.

7. Conclusions

This review surveyed 146 QSAR and machine learning studies addressing cardiac ion channel prediction over 25 years (2001–early 2026). The central finding is a historical misalignment between computational practice and multi-channel regulatory science that is now beginning to close.

The near-exclusive focus on hERG persisted far longer than data availability justified. Nav1.5 data exceeded what early hERG modelling efforts required, yet the channel received little modelling attention until 2020. This persistence reflects regulatory incentives, research inertia, and community infrastructure rather than a rational allocation of effort. The CiPA initiative articulated the need for multi-channel assessment in 2013; computational research took nearly a decade to respond on a larger scale.

Since 2022, multi-channel modelling has expanded rapidly, with hERG, Nav1.5, and Cav1.2 now modelled jointly by multiple groups. Two CiPA channels — Kv4.3 and Kir2.1 — remain entirely unmodelled in QSAR/ML literature, while the models for Kv7.1 remain scarce.

Closing the gap will require data release (or federated learning) for neglected channels, methods for data-scarce targets, and standardised benchmarks. The methodological foundations exist, but translating them into a comprehensive multi-channel modelling ecosystem depends on community coordination, particularly around data sharing.

8. Limitations

This review is based on literature searches on Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science, supplemented by forward and backward citation tracking. Despite these efforts, relevant studies may have been missed, particularly those in non-English publications, conference proceedings, or proprietary pharmaceutical research. The apparent scarcity of multi-channel modelling may partially reflect publication bias or proprietary work rather than a true lack of activity. The scope was limited to ligand-based QSAR and machine learning approaches. Structure-based methods (molecular docking and molecular dynamics) were excluded; relevant structure-based multi-target safety assessment studies may exist but were not captured. We catalogued methods and targets but did not perform quantitative meta-analysis of reported model performance. However, given the lack of standardised benchmarks and inconsistent evaluation metrics between studies, such a comparison would have limited validity. Researchers aware of work not captured in this survey are encouraged to contact the authors.

9. Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available and includes:

1. **Table S1.** Complete catalogue of 146 QSAR studies on cardiac ion channels (2001–early 2026), including study type, models, molecular descriptors, and target channels.
2. **Table S2.** Summary of datasets used in cardiac ion channel QSAR, including dataset size, activity thresholds, data types, and sources.

3. **Table S3.** Summary of data, code, models, and platform availability for each investigated study.
4. **Note S1.** ChEMBL data extraction and curation.

10. Funding

This study was funded by the Horizon Europe funding programme, under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Doctoral Networks grant agreement “Explainable AI for Molecules - Ai-Chemist” no. 101120466.

11. Author Contributions

Conceptualization: MI; *Methodology:* MI; *Investigation:* all authors; *Writing - Original Draft:* MI; *Writing - Review & Editing:* MI, FG, PR, AP, MGL, AR; *Visualization:* MI; *Supervision:* FG, PR, AP, MGL, AR; *Funding acquisition:* FG, PR, AP, MGL, AR.

12. References

- [1] F. De Ponti, E. Poluzzi, and N. Montanaro, “Organising evidence on qt prolongation and occurrence of torsades de pointes with non-antiarrhythmic drugs: a call for consensus,” *European Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, vol. 57, p. 185–209, June 2001.
- [2] H. Hishigaki and S. Kuhara, “hergapdbase: a database documenting herg channel inhibitory potentials and apd-prolongation activities of chemical compounds,” *Database*, vol. 2011, p. bar017–bar017, May 2011.
- [3] M. C. Sanguinetti and M. Tristani-Firouzi, “herg potassium channels and cardiac arrhythmia,” *Nature*, vol. 440, p. 463–469, Mar. 2006.
- [4] W. Redfern, L. Carlsson, A. Davis, W. Lynch, I. Mackenzie, S. Palethorpe, P. Siegl, I. Strang, A. Sullivan, and R. Wallis, “Relationships between preclinical cardiac electrophysiology, clinical QT interval prolongation and torsade de pointes for a broad range of drugs: evidence for a provisional safety margin in drug development,” *Cardiovasc. Res.*, vol. 58, pp. 32–45, Apr. 2003.
- [5] I. C. for Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use, “Ich harmonised tripartite guideline: The non-clinical evaluation of the potential for delayed ventricular repolarization (qt interval prolongation) by human pharmaceutical (s7b),” may 2005.
- [6] I. C. for Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use, “Ich harmonised tripartite guideline: The clinical evaluation of qt/qtC interval prolongation and proarrhythmic potential for non-antiarrhythmic drugs (e14),” may 2005.
- [7] B. Darpo and G. Ferber, “The new s7b/e14 question and answer draft guidance for industry: Contents and commentary,” *The Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, vol. 61, p. 1261–1273, June 2021.
- [8] A. A. Johnson and M. C. Trudeau, “Inhibition of herg k channels by verapamil at physiological temperature: Implications for the cipa initiative,” *Journal of Pharmacological and Toxicological Methods*, vol. 130, p. 107562, Nov. 2024.

- [9] A. Siwek, M. Marcinkowska, M. Głuch-Lutwin, B. Mordyl, M. Wolak, M. Jastrzębska-Więsek, N. Wilczyńska-Zawal, E. Wyska, K. Szafrńska, T. Karcz, O. Ostrowska, A. Bucki, and M. Kołaczkowski, "Dual 5-HT₆/serotonin ligands for mitigating neuropsychiatric symptoms of dementia exerting neuroprotection against amyloid-toxicity, memory preservation, and antidepressant-like properties," *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, vol. 275, p. 116601, 2024.
- [10] G. R. Mirams, Y. Cui, A. Sher, M. Fink, J. Cooper, B. M. Heath, N. C. McMahon, D. J. Gavaghan, and D. Noble, "Simulation of multiple ion channel block provides improved early prediction of compounds' clinical torsadogenic risk," *Cardiovascular Research*, vol. 91, p. 53–61, Feb. 2011.
- [11] J. Kramer, C. A. Obejero-Paz, G. Myatt, Y. A. Kuryshev, A. Bruening-Wright, J. S. Verducci, and A. M. Brown, "Mice models: Superior to the herg model in predicting torsade de pointes," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 3, July 2013.
- [12] W. J. Crumb, J. Vicente, L. Johannesen, and D. G. Strauss, "An evaluation of 30 clinical drugs against the comprehensive in vitro proarrhythmia assay (cipa) proposed ion channel panel," *Journal of Pharmacological and Toxicological Methods*, vol. 81, p. 251–262, Sept. 2016.
- [13] P. T. Sager, G. Gintant, J. R. Turner, S. Pettit, and N. Stockbridge, "Rechanneling the cardiac proarrhythmia safety paradigm: A meeting report from the cardiac safety research consortium," *American Heart Journal*, vol. 167, p. 292–300, Mar. 2014.
- [14] T. Colatsky, B. Fermini, G. Gintant, J. B. Pierson, P. Sager, Y. Sekino, D. G. Strauss, and N. Stockbridge, "The comprehensive in vitro proarrhythmia assay (cipa) initiative — update on progress," *Journal of Pharmacological and Toxicological Methods*, vol. 81, p. 15–20, Sept. 2016.
- [15] R. Wallis, C. Benson, B. Darpo, G. Gintant, Y. Kanda, K. Prasad, D. G. Strauss, and J.-P. Valentin, "Cipa challenges and opportunities from a non-clinical, clinical and regulatory perspectives. an overview of the safety pharmacology scientific discussion," *Journal of Pharmacological and Toxicological Methods*, vol. 93, p. 15–25, Sept. 2018.
- [16] Y. Ji, L. Johannesen, and C. Garnett, "FDA's insights: implementing new strategies for evaluating drug-induced qtc prolongation," *Journal of Pharmacokinetics and Pharmacodynamics*, vol. 52, June 2025.
- [17] K. C. Chang, S. Dutta, G. R. Mirams, K. A. Beattie, J. Sheng, P. N. Tran, M. Wu, W. W. Wu, T. Colatsky, D. G. Strauss, and Z. Li, "Uncertainty quantification reveals the importance of data variability and experimental design considerations for in silico proarrhythmia risk assessment," *Frontiers in Physiology*, vol. 8, Nov. 2017.
- [18] M. Lei, L. Wu, D. A. Terrar, and C. L.-H. Huang, "The modernized classification of cardiac antiarrhythmic drugs: Its application to clinical practice," *Heart Rhythm*, vol. 22, p. e500–e506, Aug. 2025.
- [19] F. De Ponti, "Pharmacological and regulatory aspects of qt prolongation," Jan. 2008.
- [20] A. Cavalli, E. Poluzzi, F. De Ponti, and M. Recanatini, "Toward a pharmacophore for drugs inducing the long qt syndrome: Insights from a comfa study of herg k⁺ channel blockers," *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, vol. 45, p. 3844–3853, July 2002.
- [21] S. Ekins, W. J. Crumb, R. D. Sarazan, J. H. Wikel, and S. A. Wrighton, "Three-dimensional quantitative structure-activity relationship for inhibition of human ether-a-go-go-related gene potassium channel," *The Journal of Pharmacology and Experimental Therapeutics*, vol. 301, p. 427–434, May 2002.
- [22] O. Roche, G. Trube, J. Zuegge, P. Pflimlin, A. Alanine, and G. Schneider, "A virtual screening method for prediction of the herg potassium channel liability of compound libraries," *ChemBioChem*, vol. 3, p. 455, May 2002.
- [23] A. M. Aronov and B. B. Goldman, "A model for identifying herg k⁺ channel blockers," *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, vol. 12, p. 2307–2315, May 2004.
- [24] W. Bains, A. Basman, and C. White, "Herg binding specificity and binding site structure: evidence from a fragment-based evolutionary computing study," *Progress in Biophysics and Molecular Biology*, vol. 86, p. 205–233, Oct. 2004.
- [25] M. Song and M. Clark, "Development and evaluation of an in silico model for herg binding," *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, vol. 46, p. 392–400, Dec. 2006.
- [26] E. Dubus, I. Ijjaali, F. Petitet, and A. Michel, "In silico classification of herg channel blockers: a knowledge-based strategy," *ChemMedChem*, vol. 1, p. 622–630, May 2006.
- [27] M. Tobita, T. Nishikawa, and R. Nagashima, "A discriminant model constructed by the support vector machine method for herg potassium channel inhibitors," *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters*, vol. 15, p. 2886–2890, June 2005.
- [28] C. Kramer, B. Beck, J. Kriegl, and T. Clark, "A composite model for herg blockade," *ChemMedChem*, vol. 3, p. 254–265, Feb. 2008.
- [29] B. Nisius, A. H. Göller, and J. Bajorath, "Combining cluster analysis, feature selection and multiple support vector machine models for the identification of human ether-a-go-go related gene channel blocking compounds," *Chemical Biology & Drug Design*, vol. 73, p. 17–25, Jan. 2009.
- [30] O. Obrezanova, G. Csányi, J. M. R. Gola, and M. D. Segall, "Gaussian processes: A method for automatic qsar modeling of adme properties," *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, vol. 47, p. 1847–1857, June 2007.
- [31] K.-M. Thai and G. F. Ecker, "A binary qsar model for classification of herg potassium channel blockers," *Bioorganic and Medicinal Chemistry*, vol. 16, p. 4107–4119, Apr. 2008.
- [32] K.-M. Thai and G. F. Ecker, "Similarity-based siba descriptors for classification of chemically diverse herg blockers," *Molecular Diversity*, vol. 13, p. 321–336, Feb. 2009.
- [33] E. Fioravanzo, N. Cazzolla, L. Durando, C. Ferrari, M. Mabilia, R. Ombrato, and M. D. Parenti, "General and independent approaches to predict herg affinity values," *Internet Electronic Journal of Molecular Design*, vol. 2, 2004.

- [34] G. Cianchetta, Y. Li, J. Kang, D. Rampe, A. Fravolini, G. Cruciani, and R. J. Vaz, "Predictive models for hERG potassium channel blockers," *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters*, vol. 15, p. 3637–3642, Aug. 2005.
- [35] G. Ermondi, S. Visentin, and G. Caron, "Grind-based 3d-qsar and comfa to investigate topics dominated by hydrophobic interactions: The case of hERG k⁺ channel blockers," *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, vol. 44, p. 1926–1932, May 2009.
- [36] G. M. Keserü, "Prediction of hERG potassium channel affinity by traditional and hologram qsar methods," *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters*, vol. 13, p. 2773–2775, Aug. 2003.
- [37] A. Coi, I. Massarelli, L. Murgia, M. Saraceno, V. Calderone, and A. M. Bianucci, "Prediction of hERG potassium channel affinity by the codessa approach," *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, vol. 14, p. 3153–3159, May 2006.
- [38] M. Seierstad and D. K. Agrafiotis, "A qsar model of hERG binding using a large, diverse, and internally consistent training set," *Chemical Biology & Drug Design*, vol. 67, p. 284–296, Apr. 2006.
- [39] S. Ekins, "In silico approaches to predicting drug metabolism, toxicology and beyond," *Biochemical Society Transactions*, vol. 31, p. 611–614, June 2003.
- [40] R. A. Pearlstein, R. J. Vaz, J. Kang, X.-L. Chen, M. Preobrazhenskaya, A. E. Shchekotikhin, A. M. Korablev, L. N. Lysenkova, O. V. Miroshnikova, J. Hendrix, and D. Rampe, "Characterization of hERG potassium channel inhibition using comsia 3d qsar and homology modeling approaches," *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters*, vol. 13, p. 1829–1835, May 2003.
- [41] M. K. Leong, "A novel approach using pharmacophore ensemble/support vector machine (phe/svm) for prediction of hERG liability," *Chemical Research in Toxicology*, vol. 20, p. 217–226, Jan. 2007.
- [42] K. Hansen, F. Rathke, T. Schroeter, G. Rast, T. Fox, J. M. Kriegl, and S. Mika, "Bias-correction of regression models: A case study on hERG inhibition," *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, vol. 49, p. 1486–1496, May 2009.
- [43] A. Aptula and M. Cronin, "Prediction of hERG k⁺ blocking potency: Application of structural knowledge," *SAR and QSAR in Environmental Research*, vol. 15, p. 399–411, Oct. 2004.
- [44] M. M. Gepp and M. C. Hutter, "Determination of hERG channel blockers using a decision tree," *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, vol. 14, p. 5325–5332, Aug. 2006.
- [45] M. Wang, X. Yang, and Y. Xue, "Identifying hERG potassium channel inhibitors by machine learning methods," *QSAR & Combinatorial Science*, vol. 27, p. 1028–1035, Aug. 2008.
- [46] A. Coi, I. Massarelli, M. Saraceno, N. Carli, L. Testai, V. Calderone, and A. M. Bianucci, "Quantitative structure–activity relationship models for predicting biological properties, developed by combining structure- and ligand-based approaches: An application to the human ether-a-go-go-related gene potassium channel inhibition," *Chemical Biology & Drug Design*, vol. 74, p. 416–433, Sept. 2009.
- [47] B. Nisius and A. H. Göller, "Similarity-based classifier using topomers to provide a knowledge base for hERG channel inhibition," *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, vol. 49, p. 247–256, Jan. 2009.
- [48] H. Sun, "An accurate and interpretable bayesian classification model for prediction of hERG liability," *ChemMedChem*, vol. 1, p. 315–322, Mar. 2006.
- [49] B. Zdrazil, E. Felix, F. Hunter, E. J. Manners, J. Blackshaw, S. Corbett, M. de Veij, H. Ioannidis, D. M. Lopez, J. F. Mosquera, M. P. Magarinos, N. Bosc, R. Arcila, T. Kizilören, A. Gaulton, A. P. Bento, M. F. Adasme, P. Monecke, G. A. Landrum, and A. R. Leach, "The ChEMBL Database in 2023: a drug discovery platform spanning multiple bioactivity data types and time periods," *Nucleic Acids Research*, vol. 52, pp. D1180–D1192, 11 2023.
- [50] S. Kim, J. Chen, T. Cheng, A. Gindulyte, J. He, S. He, Q. Li, B. Shoemaker, P. Thiessen, B. Yu, L. Zaslavsky, J. Zhang, and E. Bolton, "Pubchem 2025 update," *Nucleic Acids Research*, vol. 53, p. D1516–D1525, Nov. 2024.
- [51] M. Doddareddy, E. Klaasse, Shagufta, A. IJzerman, and A. Bender, "Prospective validation of a comprehensive in silico hERG model and its applications to commercial compound and drug databases," *ChemMedChem*, vol. 5, p. 716–729, Apr. 2010.
- [52] P. Czodrowski, "hERG me out," *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, vol. 53, p. 2240–2251, Aug. 2013.
- [53] R. Didziapetris and K. Lanevskij, "Compilation and physicochemical classification analysis of a diverse hERG inhibition database," *Journal of Computer-Aided Molecular Design*, vol. 30, p. 1175–1188, Oct. 2016.
- [54] R. L. Marchese Robinson, R. C. Glen, and J. B. O. Mitchell, "Development and comparison of hERG blocker classifiers: Assessment on different datasets yields markedly different results," *Molecular Informatics*, vol. 30, p. 443–458, May 2011.
- [55] F. Broccatelli, R. Mannhold, A. Moriconi, S. Giuli, and E. Carosati, "Qsar modeling and data mining link torsades de pointes risk to the interplay of extent of metabolism, active transport, and hERG liability," *Molecular Pharmaceutics*, vol. 9, p. 2290–2301, July 2012.
- [56] R. Braga, V. Alves, M. Silva, E. Muratov, D. Fourches, A. Tropsha, and C. Andrade, "Tuning hERG out: Antitarget qsar models for drug development," *Current Topics in Medicinal Chemistry*, vol. 14, p. 1399–1415, June 2014.
- [57] H. Sun, R. Huang, M. Xia, S. Shahane, N. Southall, and Y. Wang, "Prediction of hERG liability – using svm classification, bootstrapping and jackknifing," *Molecular Informatics*, vol. 36, Dec. 2017.
- [58] B. Wiśniowska *et al.*, "Randomforest based assessment of the hERG channel inhibition potential for the early drug cardiotoxicity testing," *Bio-Algorithms and Med-Systems*, vol. 6, no. 12-Supplement, pp. 211–212, 2010.
- [59] V. B. Siramshetty, Q. Chen, P. Devarakonda, and R. Preissner, "The catch-22 of predicting hERG blockade using publicly accessible bioactivity data," *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, vol. 58, p. 1224–1233, May 2018.

- [60] L. Du-Cuny, L. Chen, and S. Zhang, "A critical assessment of combined ligand- and structure-based approaches to hERG channel blocker modeling," *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, vol. 51, p. 2948–2960, Oct. 2011.
- [61] S. Chavan, A. Abdelaziz, J. G. Wiklander, and I. A. Nicholls, "A k-nearest neighbor classification of hERG k⁺ channel blockers," *Journal of Computer-Aided Molecular Design*, vol. 30, p. 229–236, Feb. 2016.
- [62] V. M. Alves, A. Golbraikh, S. J. Capuzzi, K. Liu, W. I. Lam, D. R. Korn, D. Pozefsky, C. H. Andrade, E. N. Muratov, and A. Tropsha, "Multi-descriptor read across (mudra): A simple and transparent approach for developing accurate quantitative structure–activity relationship models," *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, vol. 58, p. 1214–1223, May 2018.
- [63] J. Ma, R. P. Sheridan, A. Liaw, G. E. Dahl, and V. Svetnik, "Deep neural nets as a method for quantitative structure-activity relationships," *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, vol. 55, p. 263–274, Feb. 2015.
- [64] S. Wacker and S. Y. Noskov, "Performance of machine learning algorithms for qualitative and quantitative prediction drug blockade of hERG1 channel," *Computational Toxicology*, vol. 6, p. 55–63, May 2018.
- [65] C. Zhang, Y. Zhou, S. Gu, Z. Wu, W. Wu, C. Liu, K. Wang, G. Liu, W. Li, P. W. Lee, and Y. Tang, "In silico prediction of hERG potassium channel blockage by chemical category approaches," *Toxicology Research*, vol. 5, no. 2, p. 570–582, 2016.
- [66] X. Li, Y. Zhang, H. Li, and Y. Zhao, "Modeling of the hERG k⁺ channel blockage using online chemical database and modeling environment (ochem)," *Molecular Informatics*, vol. 36, Aug. 2017.
- [67] J.-H. Kim, C.-H. Chae, S.-M. Kang, J.-Y. Lee, G.-N. Lee, S.-H. Hwang, and N.-S. Kang, "The predictive QSAR model for hERG inhibitors using Bayesian and random forest classification method," *Bulletin of the Korean Chemical Society*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 1237–1240, 2011.
- [68] S. Wang, Y. Li, J. Wang, L. Chen, L. Zhang, H. Yu, and T. Hou, "Admet evaluation in drug discovery. 12. development of binary classification models for prediction of hERG potassium channel blockage," *Molecular Pharmaceutics*, vol. 9, p. 996–1010, Mar. 2012.
- [69] L.-l. Liu, J. Lu, Y. Lu, M.-y. Zheng, X.-m. Luo, W.-l. Zhu, H.-l. Jiang, and K.-x. Chen, "Novel Bayesian classification models for predicting compounds blocking hERG potassium channels," *Acta Pharmacologica Sinica*, vol. 35, p. 1093–1102, June 2014.
- [70] S. Polak, B. Wiśniowska, A. Glinka, K. Fijorek, and A. Mendyk, "Slow delayed rectifying potassium current (I_{Ks}) – analysis of the in vitro inhibition data and predictive model development," *Journal of Applied Toxicology*, vol. 33, p. 723–739, Feb. 2012.
- [71] B. Wiśniowska, A. Mendyk, K. Fijorek, A. Glinka, and S. Polak, "Predictive model for I-type channel inhibition: multichannel block in QT prolongation risk assessment," *Journal of Applied Toxicology*, vol. 32, no. 10, p. 858–866, 2012.
- [72] C. Obiol-Pardo, J. Gomis-Tena, F. Sanz, J. Saiz, and M. Pastor, "A multiscale simulation system for the prediction of drug-induced cardiotoxicity," *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, vol. 51, p. 483–492, Jan. 2011.
- [73] R. P. Sheridan, W. M. Wang, A. Liaw, J. Ma, and E. M. Gifford, "Extreme gradient boosting as a method for quantitative structure-activity relationships," *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, vol. 56, p. 2353–2360, Dec. 2016.
- [74] J. Hu, M. Huang, N. Ono, Y. Chen-Izu, L. T. Izu, and S. Kanaya, "Cardiotoxicity prediction based on integrated hERG database with molecular convolution model," in *2019 IEEE International Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedicine (BIBM)*, p. 1500–1503, IEEE, Nov. 2019.
- [75] J. Y. Ryu, M. Y. Lee, J. H. Lee, B. H. Lee, and K.-S. Oh, "Deephit: a deep learning framework for prediction of hERG-induced cardiotoxicity," *Bioinformatics*, vol. 36, p. 3049–3055, Feb. 2020.
- [76] A. Karim, M. Lee, T. Balle, and A. Sattar, "Cardiotox net: a robust predictor for hERG channel blockade based on deep learning meta-feature ensembles," *Journal of Cheminformatics*, vol. 13, Aug. 2021.
- [77] Z. Wu, D. Jiang, J. Wang, C.-Y. Hsieh, D. Cao, and T. Hou, "Mining toxicity information from large amounts of toxicity data," *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, vol. 64, p. 6924–6936, May 2021.
- [78] G. Xiong, Z. Wu, J. Yi, L. Fu, Z. Yang, C. Hsieh, M. Yin, X. Zeng, C. Wu, A. Lu, X. Chen, T. Hou, and D. Cao, "Admetlab 2.0: an integrated online platform for accurate and comprehensive predictions of ADMET properties," *Nucleic Acids Research*, vol. 49, p. W5–W14, Apr. 2021.
- [79] H. Kim, M. Park, I. Lee, and H. Nam, "BayeshERG: a robust, reliable and interpretable deep learning model for predicting hERG channel blockers," *Briefings in Bioinformatics*, vol. 23, June 2022.
- [80] E. Ylipää, S. Chavan, M. Bänkestad, J. Broberg, B. Glinghammar, U. Norinder, and I. Cotgreave, "hERG-toxicity prediction using traditional machine learning and advanced deep learning techniques," *Current Research in Toxicology*, vol. 5, p. 100121, 2023.
- [81] Y. Wang, L. Huang, S. Jiang, Y. Wang, J. Zou, H. Fu, and S. Yang, "Capsule networks showed excellent performance in the classification of hERG blockers/nonblockers," *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, vol. 10, Jan. 2020.
- [82] L. Liu, Q. Zhang, and Y. Wei, "Mtf-HERG: A multi-type features fusion-based framework for predicting hERG cardiotoxicity of compounds," *IEEE Transactions on Computational Biology and Bioinformatics*, vol. 22, p. 3202–3212, Nov. 2025.
- [83] J.-W. Chu, J.-H. Park, and Y.-R. Cho, "Memol: Mixture of experts for multimodal learning through multi-head attention to predict drug toxicity," *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*, vol. 273, p. 109088, Jan. 2026.

- [84] V. B. Siramshetty, D.-T. Nguyen, N. J. Martinez, N. T. Southall, A. Simeonov, and A. V. Zakharov, "Critical assessment of artificial intelligence methods for prediction of hERG channel inhibition in the "big data" era," *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, vol. 60, p. 6007–6019, Dec. 2020.
- [85] T. Wang, J. Sun, and Q. Zhao, "Investigating cardiotoxicity related with hERG channel blockers using molecular fingerprints and graph attention mechanism," *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, vol. 153, p. 106464, Feb. 2023.
- [86] I. Arab, K. Egghe, K. Laukens, K. Chen, K. Barakat, and W. Bittremieux, "Benchmarking of small molecule feature representations for hERG, nav1.5, and cav1.2 cardiotoxicity prediction," *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, vol. 64, p. 2515–2527, Oct. 2023.
- [87] T. Wang, Z. Du, L. Zhuo, X. Fu, Q. Zou, and X. Yao, "Multicblo: Enhancing predictions of compound-induced inhibition of cardiac ion channels with advanced multimodal learning," *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, vol. 276, p. 133825, Sept. 2024.
- [88] L. Feng, X. Fu, Z. Du, Y. Guo, L. Zhuo, Y. Yang, D. Cao, and X. Yao, "Multictox: Empowering accurate cardiotoxicity prediction through adaptive multimodal learning," *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, vol. 65, p. 3517–3528, Mar. 2025.
- [89] G. W. Kyro, M. T. Martin, E. D. Watt, and V. S. Batista, "Cardiogenai: a machine learning-based framework for re-engineering drugs for reduced hERG liability," *Journal of Cheminformatics*, vol. 17, Mar. 2025.
- [90] D. Lee and S. Yoo, "hergat: predicting hERG blockers using graph attention mechanism through atom- and molecule-level interaction analyses," *Journal of Cheminformatics*, vol. 17, Jan. 2025.
- [91] S. Mohammad, V. Chandrasekar, O. Aboumarzouk, A. Vikram Singh, and S. Prasad Dakua, "Leveraging machine and deep learning algorithms for hERG blocker prediction," *IEEE Access*, vol. 13, p. 81018–81028, 2025.
- [92] S. He, X. Ye, and T. Sakurai, "CloP-herg: The contrastive learning optimized pre-trained model for representation learning in predicting drug-induced hERG channel blockers," *Medinformatics*, vol. 1, p. 103–111, Jan. 2024.
- [93] D. Hossain, F. Al Abir, and J. Y. Chen, "herg-ltn: A new paradigm in hERG cardiotoxicity assessment using neuro-symbolic and generative AI embedding (megamolbart, llama3.2, gemini, deepseek) approach," Feb. 2025.
- [94] N. Khalifa, L. S. Kumar Konda, and R. Kristam, "Machine learning-based QSAR models to predict sodium ion channel (nav1.5) blockers," *Future Medicinal Chemistry*, vol. 12, p. 1829–1843, Oct. 2020.
- [95] W. Kong, W. Huang, C. Peng, B. Zhang, G. Duan, W. Ma, and Z. Huang, "Multiple machine learning methods aided virtual screening of nav1.5 inhibitors," *Journal of Cellular and Molecular Medicine*, vol. 27, p. 266–276, Dec. 2022.
- [96] I. Arab and K. Barakat, "Toxtree: descriptor-based machine learning models for both hERG and nav1.5 cardiotoxicity liability predictions," 2021.
- [97] I. Arab, K. Laukens, and W. Bittremieux, "Semisupervised learning to boost hERG, nav1.5, and cav1.2 cardiac ion channel toxicity prediction by mining a large unlabeled small molecule data set," *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, vol. 64, p. 6410–6420, Aug. 2024.
- [98] Z. Chen, N. Li, P. Zhang, Y. Li, and X. Li, "Cardiodpi: An explainable deep-learning model for identifying cardiotoxic chemicals targeting hERG, cav1.2, and nav1.5 channels," *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, vol. 474, p. 134724, Aug. 2024.
- [99] N. Gambacorta, F. Mastrolorito, M. V. Togo, V. Amenduni, M. Mele, A. Liantonio, A. Mele, A. De Luca, C. D. Altomare, V. Belgiovine, A. R. Tondo, F. Cutropia, L. Siragusa, N. Amoroso, F. Ciriaco, P. Imbrici, D. Trisciuzzi, and O. Nicolotti, "Cupid: A free drug discovery platform for the explainable multi-ion channel assessment of cardiotoxicity," *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, vol. 290, p. 117575, June 2025.
- [100] C. Cai, P. Guo, Y. Zhou, J. Zhou, Q. Wang, F. Zhang, J. Fang, and F. Cheng, "Deep learning-based prediction of drug-induced cardiotoxicity," *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, vol. 59, p. 1073–1084, Feb. 2019.
- [101] L. S. K. Konda, S. Keerthi Praba, and R. Kristam, "hERG liability classification models using machine learning techniques," *Computational Toxicology*, vol. 12, p. 100089, Nov. 2019.
- [102] T. M. Creanza, P. Delre, N. Ancona, G. Lentini, M. Saviano, and G. F. Mangiatordi, "Structure-based prediction of hERG-related cardiotoxicity: A benchmark study," *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, vol. 61, p. 4758–4770, Sept. 2021.
- [103] O. B. McManus, M. L. Garcia, D. Weaver, M. Bryant, S. Titus, and J. B. Herrington, "Ion channel screening," in *Assay Guidance Manual*, Bethesda, MD: Eli Lilly & Company and the National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences, Oct. 2012. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK100915/>.
- [104] D. Nagy, A. Lindqvist, M. Christensen, and G. Mattson, "Temperature effect on hERG channel pharmacology measured using the qube automated patch clamp system," *Journal of Pharmacological and Toxicological Methods*, vol. 135, p. 107803, 2025.
- [105] I. Smit, M. F. Adasme, E. Manners, S. Corbett, N. Bosc, H.-M.-A. Do, A. R. Leach, N. M. O'Boyle, and B. Zdzrazil, "Integrating artificial intelligence and manual curation to enhance bioassay annotations in ChEMBL," *Journal of Cheminformatics*, vol. 18, Feb. 2026.
- [106] I. C. for Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use, "E14/s7b questions and answers: Clinical and nonclinical evaluation of QT/QTc interval prolongation and proarrhythmic potential," march 2022.

- [107] Z. Wu, B. Ramsundar, E. Feinberg, J. Gomes, C. Geniesse, A. S. Pappu, K. Leswing, and V. Pande, "Moleculenet: a benchmark for molecular machine learning," *Chemical Science*, vol. 9, no. 2, p. 513–530, 2018.
- [108] A. Kryshchuk, T. Schwede, M. Topf, K. Fidelis, and J. Moult, "Critical assessment of methods of protein structure prediction (casp)—round xiii," *Proteins: Structure, Function, and Bioinformatics*, vol. 87, p. 1011–1020, Oct. 2019.
- [109] T. Hanser, E. Ahlberg, A. Amberg, L. T. Anger, C. Barber, R. J. Brennan, A. Brigo, A. Delaunois, S. Glowienke, N. Greene, L. Johnston, D. Kuhn, L. Kuhnke, J.-F. Marchaland, W. Muster, J. Plante, F. Rippmann, Y. Sabinis, F. Schmidt, R. van Deursen, S. Werner, A. White, J. Wichard, and T. Yukawa, "Data-driven federated learning in drug discovery with knowledge distillation," *Nature Machine Intelligence*, vol. 7, p. 423–436, Mar. 2025.
- [110] M. Stanley, J. F. Bronskill, K. Maziarz, H. Misztela, J. Lanini, M. Segler, N. Schneider, and M. Brockschmidt, "FS-Mol: A few-shot learning dataset of molecules," in *Thirty-fifth Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS) Datasets and Benchmarks Track*, 2021.
- [111] H. Altae-Tran, B. Ramsundar, A. S. Pappu, and V. Pande, "Low data drug discovery with one-shot learning," *ACS Central Science*, vol. 3, p. 283–293, Apr. 2017.
- [112] T. O'Hara, L. Virág, A. Varró, and Y. Rudy, "Simulation of the undiseased human cardiac ventricular action potential: Model formulation and experimental validation," *PLoS Computational Biology*, vol. 7, p. e1002061, May 2011.